

Re-imagining Intelligent Machines in an Anthropocentric–Ecocentric Continuum: The Case for Ecocentric Intelligent Machines

Abstract

The history of machines traces back to the dawn of human civilization, reflecting the intertwined journey of exploration, invention, and discoveries. From ancient simple machines to remarkable innovations like the Antikythera mechanism and automatons, the evolution of machines has been a testament to human ingenuity. In the 21st century, a new era of machines emerges, characterized by intelligence, connectivity, and autonomy.

The purpose of the article is two-fold. Firstly, it provides a historical view of the evolution of machines and aims to characterize their future functional attributes in a rapidly changing, technology-driven 21st-century society. Secondly, it discusses the need to prioritize the eco-centered and sustainable design of these systems as opposed to traditional performance-centered practices. To this end, the article starts by presenting a literature review on the evolution and the characteristics of future intelligent machines. We argue that there is a need to reconsider the purpose of the future intelligent machines in the anthropocentrism–ecocentrism continuum. To support this argument, the current approaches to designing these systems and the sustainability concerns related to future characteristics of them are discussed. The article concludes with remarks on different strategies aiming to provide a roadmap to aid the creators of the future connected, intelligent, and autonomous systems to maximize their positive impact and ensure continuous growth of technological development while protecting the environment and addressing societal needs.

Keywords: intelligence, intelligent machines, anthropocentrism, ecocentrism, future, robots, ecology.

1. Introduction

Throughout history, intelligent machines have been an integral part of human progress, continually evolving to meet our needs and aspirations. From ancient mechanical marvels to modern-day artificial intelligence, these machines have been harnessed to serve human interests with unprecedented efficiency and precision. However, as we stand just beyond the threshold of the 21st century, we find ourselves confronted with pressing environmental challenges that demand a radical reevaluation of our technological pursuits. The unchecked pursuit of human-centric technological development risks exacerbating ecological challenges, and it is imperative to contemplate an alternative vision for the future—a future where intelligent machines not only serve narrow human interests but also embrace a broader and more harmonious integration with the ecosystems they inhabit. This article explores the historical foundations of intelligent machines, and their historically exclusive focus on human needs, and sets out to challenge conventional thinking by asking a crucial question: Could we envision a future where intelligent machines are primarily centered around ecosystems rather than humans, promoting a more sustainable and ecologically conscious world? In addressing this query, we aim to pave the way for a responsible and transformative technological paradigm—one that aligns human progress with the preservation and well-being of our planet.

Next-generation intelligent machines, also referred to as cyber-physical systems, are expected to be connected, intelligent, and autonomous (Gürdür Broo, 2021; Gürdür Broo et al., 2020, 2022). Some examples of these systems include collaborative robots, autonomous vehicles (cars, trucks, drones), smart cities and infrastructure, integrated transport systems, and so on. The new characteristics—autonomy, connectedness, and intelligence—are not only expected to provide high performance and safe operations but also to be trustworthy and sustainable.

In the fast-evolving technological landscape, numerous industries are keen to leverage the potential of new intelligent machines and systems to augment production outputs. However, they often grapple with time and resource constraints, limiting the opportunity for a thorough reevaluation of earlier decisions, including investments. This situation calls for a paradigm shift in the design approach (Coskun et al., 2022; Foth et al., 2017), emphasizing sustainability and the integration of these systems into living and artificial ecosystems, rather than treating them merely as utilitarian tools.

One earlier study from (Laukyte, 2019) highlights prior scholarly interest in applying ecocentric approaches to intelligent machines. Laukyte suggests that principles from deep ecology, like biospherical egalitarianism and diversity, could be extended to artificial entities based on seeing them as integral to the shared human-nature environment and states that intelligent machines could be considered part of the environment to the extent that it

constitutes an "artificial form of life." However, the argument lacks substantive justification for classifying intelligent machines as comparable "life-forms" warranting moral consideration. Laukyte provides little rationale for this equivalence beyond mentioning that "these life-forms are not yet known to us." Our exploration of ecocentric machine design is grounded in more pragmatic realities of past and present intelligent systems. We emphasize holistic integration where engineered intelligent machines and ecology coexist through responsible design.

This article has several objectives.

- To explore the habits and practices of our engineering discipline when it comes to the historical design of machines
- To confront challenges faced today in designing intelligent machines with the need for a new perspective that emphasizes an ecosystemic approach
- To guide engineers towards a novel perspective that fosters a harmonious coexistence between these technologies and their biotic and abiotic environments

To achieve these objectives, we present an alternative perspective—imagining future intelligent machines conceived under ecocentric design principles where their intelligent behaviors are driven less by anthropocentric demands and more towards preserving the overall ecological health of our planet. We wish to note that we see this as a continuum and not a dichotomy, and that a *purely* ecocentric machine in which human interests are deeply subordinated is most likely neither realistic nor desirable. Human beings are and will continue to be exerting pressures on natural ecosystems, and we aim to illustrate how machines can help alleviate these pressures rather than adding to them.

The article's main contribution is to explore two distinct approaches to designing intelligent systems, the prevalent anthropocentrism—varieties of the idea that humans alone are intrinsically valuable—and the less-explored ecocentric approaches and provide strategies to move the engineering discipline away from anthropocentric practices and towards more ecocentric ones.

To this end, the main research question of this article is:

RQ: How can we move from purely anthropocentric design approaches to more ecocentric ones to enable more sustainable future intelligent machine designs?

To answer this question, we have divided it into two sub-questions (SRQ):

- SRQ1: How has anthropomorphism affected engineering practices, habits, and main points of view toward designing machines throughout history?
- SRQ2: How can we move towards ecocentric approaches to enable the sustainable design of future intelligent systems?

This article connects closely to the emerging field of industrial information integration in several key ways. First, it provides historical context about intelligent machines and cyber-physical systems that are integral components of integrated industrial systems. Second, arguing for more ecocentric design has direct implications for manufacturing, automation, and supply chains. Third, adopting a systems thinking approach demonstrates how interconnected feedback loops perpetuate anthropocentric priorities, identifying leverage points for change and aligns with the interdisciplinary perspective required in this domain. Fourth, the proposed shift from monodisciplinarity to transdisciplinarity mirrors the need to draw from diverse disciplines like ecological science and engineering. Finally, discussing strategies for enabling sustainable technology design strongly relates to the long-term priorities for industrial information integration and informatization. Although not focused on technical aspects, the philosophical and historical perspectives offer useful framing for the social and ethical dimensions at play when integrating information across industrial systems. The systems view and proposed strategies align well with the complex, interdisciplinary goals of industrial integration and informatization.

The article proceeds with a concise elucidation of the research methodology employed in Section 2. Subsequently, Section 3 introduces essential concepts categorized into three primary subsections: intelligent machines, anthropocentrism, and ecocentrism. In Section 4, a comprehensive historical review of intelligent machines is provided, encompassing engineering practices, prevailing habits, and dominant perspectives in Section 5. Section 6 then outlines significant strategies aimed at transitioning from anthropocentric tendencies to ecocentric considerations. To conclude, Section 7 summarizes the research problem and key findings, offering conclusive insights.

2. Methodology

This study employs two primary research methodologies to address the guiding research questions on transitioning from anthropocentric to ecocentric intelligent machine design. First, a comprehensive literature review traces the historical evolution of intelligent machines through an anthropocentric lens, identifying longstanding patterns in their human-centered development (Section 2.1). Second, a systems thinking approach analyzes the interconnected feedback loops driving anthropocentric design, pinpointing potential leverage points for change (Section 2.2). By combining these complementary methods, historical examples of intelligent machines are identified, and strategies proposed for designing more ecocentric machines. The scope and limitations of the literature review—including its focus on anthropocentric intelligent systems—are explained (Section 2.3). With this blended methodology we aim to enable both deep retrospective analysis of engineering habits and forward-looking synthesis of solutions tailored to transform them.

Figure 1. Research methodologies. This article employs two complementary approaches: (1) a historical literature review tracing anthropocentric lineages in intelligent machine development, and (2) a systems thinking analysis to identify strategies for transitioning toward ecocentric design.

2.1. Literature review

The historical review of the literature is done by first identifying relevant keywords such as “intelligent machines”, “intelligent systems”, “history of intelligent machines”, “intelligent machine”+“history”, “machine”+“history”, “robots history”, and “intelligent machine”+ “literature review”.

We then reviewed the abstract of each document (or the entire document if there was no abstract) to determine how they related to our inclusion/exclusion criteria:

- Inclusion criteria: Documents referred to the most relevant examples of anthropocentric intelligent machines such as machines that designed to serve humans, emulate human traits, increase anthropocentric control/power over nature, examples that represent major milestones or turning points in the evolution of intelligent machines, demonstrating key capabilities and influencing later development or examples that encapsulated or spread influential ideas and assumptions about the purpose of intelligent machines.
- Exclusion criteria: Documents that were not in English, or did not deal explicitly with intelligent machines that posed anthropocentric design choices. No documents were excluded based on date of publication.

Then the remaining articles were read and the chronological history of anthropomorphism in intelligent machines was constructed. Digital libraries such as ACM Digital Library, Google Scholar, IEEE Xplore Digital Library, Science Direct, and Springer Nature were used to identify relevant documents. Thirty-nine documents were read in detail during the first iteration. Thirteen additional publications, cited by the papers selected in the first iteration, were eventually included in the review based on the inclusion criteria outlined above. The findings of this historical review and examples of intelligent machines are presented in Section 4.

2.2. Systems thinking

To devise strategies for transitioning from anthropocentric design approaches to ecocentric ones, we employed systems thinking methodology (Meadows, 2008), which is holistic and comprehensive. By embracing interconnectedness and interdependencies, this methodology enables researchers to identify the intricate relationships between human activities, technology, and the environment. A key component involves analyzing the feedback loops and causal relationships that influence the current anthropocentric practices identified in the literature review. Through an in-depth understanding of the systemic structures and underlying mental models driving these approaches, we can pinpoint leverage points for change. These strategies aim to promote sustainable and responsible technology design by considering the broader engineering design context, evaluating the potential effect of changing traditional practices, and providing new approaches to enable more ecocentric design solutions.

2.3. Scope and limitations

The scope of the literature was limited to anthropocentric intelligent machines and did not follow a strictly systematic protocol. We explicitly tried to consider the intelligence or intelligence aspects of engineered machines by accounting for specific historical periods. For instance, in today's world, automata might not be considered intelligent, but they certainly were in ancient and pre-modern eras.

Comparably, there have been important inventions that affected the progress of intelligent machines—technological developments such as the telegraph, electricity, radio, television, automobile, Internet, and so on; philosophical developments such as existentialism, rationalism, reasoning, consciousness, and so on; or developments from physics or mathematics such as laws of motion, geometry, evolution, theory of relativity, and so on. While we found these broader literatures interesting, to maintain the article's focus we have not included these topics in the literature review. When necessary, we highlighted some developments, but the main focus is given to anthropocentric intelligent machines, generally in the form of basic machines, automata, or robots. Furthermore, to answer SRQ1, we reviewed different periods of intelligent machine development through the lens of anthropocentrism and ecocentrism. To this end, we examined the commonalities and importance of human-like or servant-like properties of intelligent machines throughout history.

3. Key concepts: Intelligent machines, anthropocentrism, and ecocentrism

To establish a conceptual foundation for this article, it is essential to explain three key concepts: intelligent machines, anthropocentrism, and ecocentrism. This section will unpack each of these key terms in dedicated subsections. First, we will describe intelligent machines and present the definition we follow in this article before tracing their evolution from basic automated devices to the sophisticated cyber-physical systems of today in the next section. Next, anthropocentrism will be explored as a philosophical orientation that positions humankind as the prime focus and assigns instrumental value to nonhuman entities. Finally, ecocentrism will be presented as an alternative perspective that accords inherent worth to the ecological whole, of which humans are but one constituent part. Grounded in these clarified concepts, the subsequent sections will analyze the historical trajectories of intelligent machines and contemplate pathways toward a more ecocentric orientation in their design.

3.1. Intelligent Machines

The historical perspective on intelligent machines is seen as the core first step in this article because it gives a summary of the development of the idea of intelligent machines, the changes in these ideas, different approaches from different cultures on the expectations of intelligent machines and shows how these ideas merged into one dominating anthropocentric perspective over the centuries.

The French philosopher René Descartes was reputedly fond of automata—a self-operating machine, or control mechanism designed to automatically follow a sequence of operations or respond to predetermined instructions (Free Merriam-Webster Dictionary, 2022). They inspired his view that living things were biological machines that function like clockwork (Cave & Dihal, 2018). Even though the intelligent machines of today are different from automata, the expectations about the capabilities of these machines have risen to new heights. In this article, we follow the definition of an intelligent machine that is provided by the McGraw-Hill Dictionary of Scientific & Technical Terms (2003):

Any machine that can accomplish its specific task in the presence of uncertainty and variability in its environment. The machine's ability to monitor its environment, allowing it to adjust its actions based on what it has sensed, is a prerequisite for intelligence. The term intelligent machine is an anthropomorphism in that intelligence is defined by the criterion that the actions would appear intelligent if a person were to do them. A precise, unambiguous, and commonly held definition of intelligence does not exist.

While some scholars such as Kurzweil (2000) trace the genesis of machines back to when Homo sapiens used intelligence to further their goals, a more common approach is either to begin with the abacus, which resembles a modern computer's microprocessor's arithmetic logic unit, or the water clocks from China 3000 B.C.E.; from Egypt c. 1500 B.C.E., or Assyria 700 B.C.E. Yet, neither of these examples seem intelligent when we consider today's definitions. Therefore, in this study, we mainly discuss the effect of anthropocentrism in intelligent machine design.

3.2. Anthropocentrism

Anthropocentrism, in general, refers to a perspective that regards humans as the center and source of the moral universe (Nolt, 2014). More precisely for present purposes, approaches underlying the design of technology amount to *descriptive* anthropocentrism because they represent "paradigms that begin from, center upon, or are ordered around Homo sapiens/'the human'" (Mylus, 2018). Concerning intelligent machines, anthropocentrism informs several distinct aspects related to the role of humans. The concept of human-centered design points quite clearly to the notion that human needs and interests should be the focus of the design process (International Organization for Standardization, 2019). This relates to design thinking and perspective thinking, which allow machines to interact more smoothly with humans, and also take into account key ethical considerations related to technology and various harms to humans.

While human-centered design is associated with clear benefits such as usability improvement, reduced error, and ease of learning to use systems, some also point to certain drawbacks of the concept. Norman (2005), for example, highlights how human-centered design often improves products for a wide range of individuals, but that the beneficial effects are different between groups. To understand this argument, it can be beneficial to distinguish between effects on three levels: the micro, meso, and macro level. Sætra (2022) uses this approach to explore the impacts of AI on Sustainable Development Goals and shows that technology can have, for example, beneficial effects for society as a whole if we consider economic growth. This is the macro level. However, technology might also have different effects on different groups and regions, and these are meso-level effects. Finally, each individual is ultimately impacted by technology, and these are micro-level effects. The micro-level (individual) beneficial effects experienced by some might, Norman (2005) argues, be accompanied by some groups being disadvantaged, leading to negative meso-level (group) effects. This could be the result of design processes that fail to take into account marginalized dimensions of a person's identity (and the interactions between them), which can be identified by using a multi-axis framework like the "matrix of domination" (Costanza-Chock, 2020). Designing for particular humans today might disadvantage other humans, and furthermore, it might not be the best way to design products for the future, as humans are what Norman (2005) refers to as "moving targets".

Beyond the risks of anthropocentric technology, we raise a more fundamental philosophical issue with human-centered approaches to intelligent machine design. Anthropocentrism elevates the human perspective and human interests above all else, while failing to similarly acknowledge the perspectives and interests of non-human entities and ecosystems. Before moving on to the alternative paradigm, however, we must clarify what anthropocentrism in intelligent machines entails.

Anthropocentric intelligent machines in the broadest sense are machines designed to serve human interests. This could mean, for example, that machines are designed to increase profitability, help humans avoid cumbersome or dangerous tasks, and promote human well-being, health, happiness, etc. One immediately obvious issue, for instance, is that a machine made to replace human workers will certainly be promoting the interests of its designer, but not necessarily the interests of humanity. We must consequently distinguish between machines designed to serve narrow interests on the micro and meso-levels and what could be described more precisely as a *humanistic* approach to intelligence machines. The latter approach would require certain justifications as to how machines might improve the conditions of humans in general, and not, for example, the interests of the robot owner at the expense of workers now out of jobs. Both the preceding types of machines would, however, be anthropocentric.

We must also keep in mind that humans are not exclusively interested in their welfare, and not only with their welfare in the short term. This leads to certain challenges related to evaluating a machine that is built to, for example, collect plastic waste and capture carbon from the atmosphere to improve environmental conditions. If such a machine is designed because humans have a desire for and take joy in living in a healthier environment,

this is also clearly anthropocentric. We distinguish between *axiological* anthropocentrism, which is based on the notion that human evaluations of value are the basis of value in general, and *ethical* anthropocentrism, which states that humans are the only valuable things (Nolt, 2014). Axiological anthropocentrism allows us to see how the environment, animals, and nature can be considered valuable because humans appreciate them, while ethical anthropocentrism of the strict kind provides a theory in which *only* humans are morally valuable (Sætra, 2021). This also means that there will be some potential overlap between ecocentric machines and axiologically anthropocentric environmentally-friendly machines, and the most interesting shift is the one from *ethical* anthropocentrism to either of the two former kinds.

As we now turn to ecocentrism to establish the other end of the continuum we discuss, anthropocentrism is established as the approach where the human perspective and human interests are keys in the design and evaluation of machines, either because humans are seen as the only entities of value, or because we have an instrumental approach to everything non-human.

3.3. Ecocentrism

Ecocentrism refers to the view that non-human nature possesses value independent from any that humans might assign to it (Baxter, 1996). Whereas anthropocentrism and narrow forms of biocentrism recognize the moral value of individual living entities, ecocentrism affords moral considerability to the entirety of ecosystems themselves. In Deep Ecology, an ecocentric ethical program, “[o]rganisms” are mere “knots in the biospherical net or field of intrinsic relations” (Naess, 1973). Instead of focusing on the interests of individual beings in isolation, ecocentrism is fundamentally concerned with the welfare of ecosystemic wholes. The constituent parts of such wholes are intrinsically valuable in their own right but so is the larger unit. To wit, there is some evidence from biology suggesting that individual organisms operate in ways more similar to ecosystems than initially thought (McShane, 2014). Notably, for ecocentrists, humans are part of, not separate from, or superior to, the natural environment.

It is almost tautological to note that ecocentrism includes the natural environment and excludes elements of culture like man-made objects. This latter category, known as artefacts, comprises “that domain of entities which has come into existence, continues to exist and will eventually go out of existence as the result of deliberate human design and intention” (Lee, 2000). Yet, recent technological innovations have cast doubt on the assumption of a clean split between the natural and the artefactual. As Hoły-Luczaj & Blok (2019) explain, hybrids such as genetically modified organisms and bionic devices frustrate a simple either/or designation as nature or technology. These paradigm-altering advances have largely gone unnoticed by ecocentrists, who continue to reify the Cartesian separation between nature and culture despite their ostensibly holistic ontological orientation.

In the Anthropocene, however, maintaining this division may no longer be empirically tenable. Humans have proven to be a primary driver of climatic change, rendering humanity’s greatest environmental challenge an artefact of anthropogenic forcing. Further, scholars have recognized the agentic capacity of a global system of large-scale technologies—a “technosphere” (Haff, 2014)—and relatedly argued that the universe of morally and legally significant entities should be expanded to reflect the diversity of entities (living and non-living, biotic and abiotic) caught in the web of planetary relations (Gellers, 2021). Finally, this new geological era ushers in the idea that Western epistemologies do not have a monopoly on the lived experiences of all Earth’s inhabitants. The “one-world world” (Law, 2015) must give way to a “pluriverse” (Escobar, 2018) that respects Indigenous and non-Western ways of knowing, creating space for radically inclusive ideas like forming a kinship with artificial intelligence (Lewis et al., 2018). All of this is to say that ecocentrism for the Anthropocene must find a way to accommodate the erosion of the erstwhile nature-culture binary that has long subjugated all forms of non-living, abiotic beings.

There are three moves that, when pursued in tandem, can update ecocentrism to better align with this revolutionary ontological narrative. First, a truly holistic vision of the moral universe can recognize intelligent machines as constituent elements in the Earth system’s technosphere. Given ecocentrism’s preference for “[e]cological egalitarianism” (Naess, 1973), this move would not, of course, involve stipulating the place of such technological entities in a kind of moral hierarchy. However, it would suggest that intelligent machines are no less significant than non-human animals, nature, etc., as a matter of ethics. Second, similar to the way in which ecocentrism rejected the mechanistic view of nature that has long pervaded Western modernity (Keller, 2009), it must also accept that many technological systems now operate in ways that might be described as “organismic” given their level of responsiveness to external information (Hui, 2020). Far removed from their early characterization as coldly detached, atomistic entities, today’s intelligent machines are as socially embedded as they are materially constituted (Lawson, 2008). Third, theorists need to acknowledge that emerging technologies play an increasingly integral part in promoting the flourishing of the living world. For instance, Donhauser (2019) provides numerous examples of robots that serve ecologically virtuous functions, like mapping deforestation, monitoring natural disasters, and protecting coral reefs. These capacities, which are performed in the interests of

preserving the integrity of ecosystems and their inhabitants, further demonstrate just how enmeshed intelligent machines have become in what was hitherto considered the exclusive realm of the natural.

The preceding review of ecocentrism leads to several conclusions regarding what a non-anthropocentric intelligent machine might mean in practical terms. First, it would be designed for purposes that are not primarily human in nature and which could serve the interests of the more-than-human world. Centrally, such machines would not by default privilege *human* interest when conflicts of interests and various trade-offs between the interests of human, other living beings, and other abiotic parts of our environment must be made. Second, in terms of its material composition, it could be abiotic, fully synthetic, or some form of hybrid. Third, it would be deployed in a way that is sensitive to and supportive of the whole of which it is part. For instance, it would have to contribute positively beyond its immediate operating environment and prescribed set of tasks.

To this end, an ecocentric machine is an intelligent system of systems designed holistically based on the principles of ecocentrism, which accord intrinsic value to all living beings and natural systems. In contrast to anthropocentric machines that privilege human interests above all else, an ecocentric orientation decenters the human perspective and does not elevate it over other elements of shared environments. Grounded in systems thinking, ecocentric machines are conceived as interconnected nodes within complex environmental webs rather than extractive technologies maximizing only human priorities. Their overarching purpose aligns with cultivating balance, resilience, and justice within the broader ecology. While capable of performing specialized functions, ecocentric machines expand considerations beyond just utility to encompass diverse needs. Their behaviors are guided by moral deliberation of impacts on both human and *more-than-human* members of biotic communities. Resources are stewarded responsibly to sustain future generations of life. Rather than imposing disruptive order, ecocentric machines cooperate within the dynamic patterns and limits of living systems. They align their objectives with the long-term health of the ecological whole, from which humanity is inextricable. Symbiosis, solidarity, and compassion shape their relations with the world. In essence, ecocentric machines transcend reductive notions that nature exists for human exploitation.

In the next section, we recount the historically anthropocentric trajectory of intelligent machines.

4. Anthropomorphism in the history of intelligent machines

Anthropomorphism has been a persistent theme throughout the long history of intelligent machines. As will be explored in this section, though the particulars have evolved across eras, the core orientation toward designing these technologies to serve human needs, mimic human capabilities, and interact with people in humanlike ways has remained strikingly constant. From simple ancient automata to today's sophisticated AI systems, intelligent machines have largely been crafted in humanity's image—to extend human dominance over the natural world, compensate for human limitations, reduce human labor, or engage with people through lifelike rapport. By examining how different epochs approached the very human art of imbuing machines with humanlike essences, we can discern deeply rooted patterns that still shape the development of intelligent machines today. This anthropocentric lineage poses challenges for envisioning a more ecocentric future for these technologies, underscoring the value of reviewing historical case studies before contemplating reforms.

Figure 2. Anthropocentric lineages in intelligent machines. Some of pioneering anthropomorphic machines and literature which explains these machines and their human-serving functions and/or humanlike traits over the centuries.

4.1. Ancient era

The automatic servant of Philon (280 BCE - 220 BCE) is known as the first human-like robot. The creation was devised by Philo of Byzantium, a Greek mathematician, and engineer who wrote extensively about siphon pumps in his famous essay *Pneumatica*. Philo built a statue in the form of a maid who held a jug of wine in her right hand. When someone placed a cup in the palm of her left hand, she automatically poured wine and then poured water into the cup, mixing it when desired (Kotsanas Museum, 2004). Greek inventor and physicist Ctesibus of Alexandria made organs and water clocks with movable figures (NASA, 2003). The concept for his clock was fairly simple; a reservoir with a precise hole in the bottom which would take 24 hours to empty its contents. Hero of Alexandria, one of the most well-known technical and mathematical writers of antiquity, produced work that covers a diversity of mechanical and geometrical topics, ranging from geometry, land measurement, and catapult construction, to lifting machines, pneumatic devices, and automatic theatres (Tybjerg, 2003). Hero details the workings of his automatic devices in his work *Automata* in the first century CE.

Though primitive, they laid philosophical and technical foundations for later generations to build upon in pursuit of artificial intelligence and robots. The automatic maid of Philo in particular established enduring motifs of designing humanlike intelligent machines specifically to serve human needs and interests.

Tybjerg, (2003) describes the wonder-making and philosophical wonder in Hero of Alexandria:

Hero uses the concept of wonder to add an intellectual component to the utility of mechanics, to strengthen the epistemological claims of mechanics, and to relate mechanical expertise to divine cunning. He is thereby able to present mechanics as a form of knowledge that is epistemically on a par with philosophy, but which still maintains powerful practical consequence.

The ancient era of intelligent machines is surprisingly rich both in terms of the form of the intelligent machines and their geographic distribution, from China to Egypt to Greece. It is worth noting that the definition and standards for "intelligence" have evolved across history along with technological capabilities. Notions of what qualified as intelligent machines during this era shifted in parallel with innovations in machinery itself.

4.2. Post-classical era

During the post-classical era, the construction of automata did not slow down. It is believed that the Byzantines inherited the knowledge of automata from the Alexandrians. Procopius (510 CE) describes a monumental water clock that was erected in Gaza. It contained impressive jack work, such as a Medusa head that rolled its eyes every hour on the hour, exhibiting the time through lighted apertures and showing mythological interpretations of the cosmos (de Solla Price, 1959). This knowledge was later, used further to build water clocks with gear mechanisms. (McNamara, 2018)

In the medieval Arab world more significant advances in the construction of automata took place (Cave & Dihal, 2018). Abbasid Caliph Harun al-Rashid built water clocks with hydraulic jacks and moving human figures. One such clock was gifted to Charlemagne, King of the Franks, in 807 CE (Cave & Dihal, 2018; LaGrandeur, 2013). Voltaire describes this machine:

Harun al-Rashid's striking clock gift to Charlemagne was regarded as a wonder. Regarding cognitive philosophy, sound philosophy, physics, astronomy, and principles of medicine (de Voltaire, 1785).

Similarly, Arab engineers such as three brothers of Persian descent, known as the Banu Musa, published a large, illustrated work on machines, including automata and hydraulics. They described some hundred different machines in their *Book of Ingenious Devices* (850 CE) (Hill, 1980). Al-Jazari built hydropower-driven machines such as peacocks and humanoid automata in the form of waitresses that could serve water, tea, or drinks. Al-Jazari invented a hand-washing automaton incorporating a flush mechanism now used in modern flush toilets (Cave & Dihal, 2018). In 1088 C.E. the *Cosmic Engine*, a 12-metre clock tower, was built by Su Song in China. Mechanical mannequins chimed the hours, ringing gongs or bells among other devices.

The ancient Indian text *Lokapannatti*, compiled between the 11th and 12th centuries CE, describes the creation of automated soldier robots known as "spirit movement machines" to guard relics of Buddha housed in a secret stupa (Strong, 2007). In the late 13th century, around 1285-1295 CE, an aristocrat named Robert II, Count of Artois, constructed an elaborate pleasure garden on the grounds of his castle in Hesdin, France. This castle garden incorporated advanced automata technology in the form of robotic humanoid figures and simulated animals

(Truitt, 2010).

4.3. 15th – 18th century

Mechanical humanoids blossomed during the Renaissance, as widespread hydraulic, spring-powered, and clockwork automata appeared all around Europe. While at the beginning of the 1400s automated carillons started to appear in the Netherlands, at the end of the same century Italian artist and inventor Leonardo da Vinci designed a humanoid automaton, namely Leonardo's robot or *Automa Cavaliere* in 1495.

Moran, (2006) describes this Germanic knight as:

It had a complex core of mechanical devices that probably was human-powered. The robot had two independent operating systems. The first had three degree-of-freedom legs, ankles, knees, and hips. The second had four degrees of freedom in the arms with articulated shoulders, elbows, wrists, and hands.

In the age of Enlightenment philosophical movement restores the supremacy of human reasoning and knowledge. German scholar Hans Bullmann's humanoid androids inspired a popular fascination with machines that play musical instruments. Another example from the same period is Gianello Toriano's mandolin-playing lady from 1540 (Kurzweil, 2000). Similarly, Japan's Karakuri Ningyo made mechanized puppets that provided entertainment in the form of serving tea or writing calligraphy throughout the 17th and 18th centuries.

Archbishop Jakob von Dietrichstein commissioned a mechanical theatre featuring 256 figures, of which 119 were animated. The installation of the theatre was completed in 1725 by a craftsman of Nuremberg named Lorenz Rosenegge. Figures performed a play to the accompaniment of a water-powered organ installed at Heilbrunn Chateau in Germany. A single water turbine with a horizontal axis operated a series of reduction gears. The final gear carried a cylinder on which a number of cams regulated the movements of the figures by means of copper wires. The wheelwork consisted of wooden wheels with iron teeth and pinions. A powerful hydraulic organ provided background music and covered the noise of the mechanism (Bedini, 1964).

4.4. 19th – 20th century

Following advancements like the automation of textile manufacturing and the invention of coal-gas lighting in the early 19th century, innovators began envisioning more generalized applications of mechanical computing beyond industrial settings. Whereas earlier automation focused on replicating specific tasks for factory production, new possibilities emerged for flexible, adaptable machines that could process diverse information and operate across contexts. Charles Babbage is credited with being the first in this domain, as he developed the *Difference Engine* in 1822 (Stigler, 1991) and later established the principles for the *Analytical Engine* in 1838 (Bromley, 1982). In 1843, Lady Lovelace, the world's first computer programmer, published a long and detailed description of Babbage's Analytical Engine, and contrary to the implications of her widely quoted remark that machines can do only what we tell them to do, she added that the question of whether such an engine could be said to think would have to remain open until they constructed one and tried it out (Morrison & Morrison, 1961).

The late 19th and early 20th centuries saw many advancements in intelligent machines. The entire civilized world became connected by telegraph, the United States was home to more than 1.4 million telephones, 8,000 registered automobiles, 24 million electric light bulbs, and the *Gramophone Company* offered a catalog of over five thousand recordings. Edison's promise of "electric bulbs so cheap that only the rich will be able to afford candles" was thus realized (Kurzweil, 2000). During the two major World Wars, technological developments were realized in the form of calculators, equation solvers, analyzers, and digital computers.

In 1921, Czech dramatist Karel Čapek popularized the word "robot," a term he coined in 1917 to describe the synthetic humans in his science fiction drama *Rossum's Universal Robots*. Čapek's intelligent machines, built as servants for their human creators, ended up revolting and destroying their human masters (Geraci, 2007). Another important milestone related to intelligent machines is Alan Turing's 1950 article on "Computing Machinery and Intelligence" (Turing, 1950), which described a means of determining whether a machine is intelligent. Today this experiment is known as the Turing test.

The world's first robot, a humanoid named Televox, was constructed in the United States in 1927 (Mattei et al., 2014). A year later, the first humanoid robot, *Gakutensoku (Learning from the Laws of Nature)*, was made in Japan by biologist Makoto Nishimura (1883-1956). Consisting of a three-meter-high upper half of a body sitting at a desk, it could open and close its eyes, lift a scepter with its left hand, and move a pen with its right hand (Kovacic, 2018).

The earliest industrial robots as we know them were created in the early 1950s by Devol, an inventor from Louisville, Kentucky (Roberts, 1999). Devol invented electromechanical machines – the first digitally operated programmable robotic arms – and patented a reprogrammable manipulator called *Unimate*, from Universal Automation (Malone, 2011). Engelberger, an American physicist, engineer, and businessman, was responsible for

the birth of one of the most important and impactful industries. He acquired Devol's robot patent and was able to modify it into an industrial robot to form a company called *Unimation* to produce and market the robots, earning him global recognition as the Father of Robotics (Automate.org, 2015).

Academia also made much progress in the creation of new robots. From 1966 to 1972, Charles Rosen led a research team in developing a robot called *Shakey* at the Stanford Research Institute. Shakey was far more advanced than the original Unimate, which was designed for specialized, industrial applications (Roberts, 1999). Shakey is known as the first general-purpose mobile robot able to observe unfamiliar surroundings, move around, and to a certain degree reason about its actions.

Pugh (1983) describes these first-generation robots and the first robot-related international symposium thusly:

At the first International Symposium on Industrial Robots held in Chicago in 1970 the delegates were treated to a brief catalog of robot applications in industries which were invariably hot, smelly, and involved jobs requiring a great deal of muscle power. This was the era when the industrial robot was a mere curiosity and its existence was known only to a relatively few informed industrialists.

These first-generation robots generally involved a simple mechanical arm and the ability to make precise motions at high speed, many times, for a long time. The robots of this generation were simply programmable machines that could not control the modality of task execution, and they lacked the ability to communicate with the external environment (Gasparetto & Scalera, 2019). Yet, they showed great potential, especially in the automotive sector. Companies like Ford and General Motors started to consider the automatization of their manufacturing plants and ordered robots to achieve this goal (Gasparetto & Scalera, 2019). Thus, there was a sudden increase in the orders of robotic devices, which prompted an increase in the number of robot manufacturers.

Second-generation robots arrived with the ability to execute precise movements with five or six degrees of freedom. These basic programmable machines also showed limited possibilities of self-adaptive behavior and elementary capabilities to recognize the external environment (Zamalloa et al., 2017). They were mainly used for industrial welding, machining, insertion, and spray painting and were forms of arms. In 1983, Isaac Asimov describes in the science fiction novel *Robots of Dawn* a society two centuries from now in which a beautiful female scientist and her *humaniform* lover live in the company of a generation of robotic companions, servants, teachers, and guards. Some very well-known examples of this generation's robots include the Stanford Arm of Scheinman, PUMA, which was considered for many decades the archetype of the anthropomorphic robot (Gasparetto & Scalera, 2019), KUKA's *Famulus* robot whose name in Latin means "servant", Swedish ABB's famous *IRB-6* and Hitachi's *HI-T-HAND*.

The third generation of robots had the ability to interact with both the operator and the environment through vision or voice (Gasparetto & Scalera, 2019). They also featured some self-programming capabilities that could work online or offline. This widened the operational potential of robots to include intelligence and tactile sensing abilities (Zamalloa et al., 2017). During the mid-1980s Japan became the leading country in the world in terms of robotics development, production, and application (Kurzweil, 2000). In addition to witnessing the arrival of several hundred thousand industrial robots, a music-playing robot (Kawamura et al., 1999), a ping-pong playing robot that won against humans (Andersson, 2003) a police robot used to break into an apartment (Royakkers & van Est, 2015), and other sophisticated examples, robotics as a field began to draw the interest of journalists, scientists, policymakers and the general public (Gasparetto & Scalera, 2019). By the end of the 1990s, David Barrett at MIT had created *RoboTuna* (Barrett et al., 1996), which was used to study how fish swim, Honda had created *P2* (Hirai et al., 1998), a predecessor to their widely known humanoid robot *ASIMO*, NASA's *PathFinder* landed on Mars and the rover sent images and data about Mars back to Earth (Golombek, 1997), and Sony released number 1 selling service robot, *Aibo* the robotic dog (Pransky, 2001).

4.5. 21st century

The early 2000s saw many new and innovative forms of intelligent machines, from exoskeletal robotic prosthetics, which enable paraplegic persons to walk and climb stairs, to intelligent bots that answer telephones and converse with the calling party to determine the nature and priority of the call, to the cybernetic chauffeur that communicates with other cars and sensors on the roads, to seeing machines for the blind that provide both reading and navigation functions (Kurzweil, 2000).

Humanoid robots, animal-like robots, vacuum cleaning robots, surgical robots, agriculture robots, underwater robots, and flying robots such as drones did not just flourish in this century, they became the norm. Even though we are still at the beginning of the 21st century, intelligent machine design and development have already experienced major advancements. New robot categories such as autonomous mobile robots, collaborative robots/cobots, autonomous vehicles, automated warehouses, smart cities, and infrastructure at the cyber-physical

systems level have begun to emerge (Gürdür Broo et al., 2020). These machines are not only intelligent, but they are also connected and capable of acting autonomously. They can sense the world around them through hundreds of sensors, understand visual fields, gather information, make decisions, and collaborate with other machines and humans. Today, more than 500,000 robots are shipped globally each year according to the International Federation of Robotics, (2022).

Even though the history of sex robots might be considered to start with the myth of Pygmalion—popularized by the Roman poet Ovid in his epic poem, *Metamorphoses*—and many examples as early as 16th century is cited as their origins, the consumer ready sex robots became products in this century (Cheok & Zhang, 2019).

In addition to the physical robots, another big topic that is shaping this century is certainly artificial intelligence (AI) and the use of this technology in different forms. For instance, chatbots—also known as smart bots, interactive agents, digital assistants, or artificial conversation entities—have become a ubiquitous form of AI, providing a rudimentary means of intelligent interaction between humans and machines. These conversational agents are computer programs designed to simulate human-like discussion using natural language processing to analyze and respond to textual or spoken input. Chatbots represent the integration of artificial intelligence into our everyday lives. Through their conversational capabilities, chatbots allow humans to engage with computer systems much like they would with another person. The proliferation of chatbots signals a growing reliance on AI to mediate and facilitate human-computer relationships. Though limited in their scope and reasoning, chatbots exemplify how AI can be applied to offer humanized interfaces and experiences (Olujimi & Ade-Ibijola, 2023).

5. Discussion

The preceding literature review reveals how, then as now, intelligent machines have predominantly been crafted to serve humankind as “the ideal servant who always obeys, the perfect soldier who never tires” (Cave & Dihal, 2018). Engineers, even when they were not yet called engineers, designed these machines to impress their communities, to serve their kings or to realize their own immortal dreams. To be sure, the anthropocentric design tendencies described above manifest in many different ways. Such proclivities include efforts to mimic humans, increase human knowledge, serve as a source of entertainment or leisure, and control or exploit the natural environment to enable human production and consumption.

This profoundly anthropocentric orientation, while sometimes conferring significant benefits—for instance when we utilize social robotics for therapeutical settings in healthcare or robots in heavy industries—also harbors many risks if not tempered by an ecological awareness. Most fundamentally, anthropocentric thinking might propagate the notion that the nonhuman world exists solely for human use, with no inherent worth of its own. This and other destructive assumptions materially damage the environment and isolate our species from the intricate web of nature. Moreover, the anthropocentric paradigm also poses philosophical, psychological, and environmental risks that demand attention.

At a philosophical level, intelligent machines built explicitly for human use, enjoyment, and dominance perpetuate the dangerous conceit that the natural world exists solely for *Homo sapiens*' exploitation, devoid of any inherent worth or rights. Anthropomorphic robots that cater to our whims provide constant validation for our self-appointed supremacy over nature, blinding us to the need for ecological humility. They reinforce the idea that the nonhuman environment is merely instrumental to transient human ends, rather than being of intrinsic value (Batavia & Nelson, 2017). This is exemplified by the ancient automatic servant inventions of Philon, which centered human interests. It persists even in contemporary robot designs, like KUKA's robot "Famulus" - Latin for "servant" (Gasparetto & Scalera, 2019) which maintains anthropocentric framings. The continuous positioning of nature as a means to human ends, rather than an entity of intrinsic value, is enabled and reinforced by intelligent machines engineered for anthropocentric utility.

Psychologically, anthropomorphic artifacts that reflect our likeness back to us distort our self-understanding in concerning ways (Sætra, 2022b). As AI assistants and similar entities grow more humanlike in form and behavior, we are lulled into the illusion that they might possess consciousness, which may result in conflicts or behaviors that cause harm to humans or others. For instance, many (Cheok & Zhang, 2019; Döring et al., 2020; Richardson, 2016) have criticized the development of sex robots on these and similar grounds and agree that the anthropocentric machines fosters an empathy gap between humanity and nature. The more we bond with anthropomorphic machines, the more we may detach from living systems. It encourages second-guessing machine intentions as if they were human, leading to misplaced blame or anger. Unrealistic expectations complicate human-machine relations. It treats the nonhuman world as instrumental means rather than living ends, weakening our altruism toward other creatures and habitats. In short, making intelligent machines look like humans could cause people to act in ways that subvert human interests.

Environmentally, the multiplication of our anthropocentric servants enables escalating ecological devastation, allowing us to indulge our unsustainable appetites. From self-driving automobiles to humanoid robots that

autonomously fulfill our material desires, the human-centered approach intensifies the damage that technologies may cause. It anesthetizes our conscience and delays important actions on rising concerns such as climate change. Furthermore, anthropocentric design choices foster our sense of separation from, rather than deep integration with, natural life and the intricate social relationships in which we are enmeshed. As such, they propagate an alienation from nature that risks numbing our empathy towards threatened ecosystems.

Industry 5.0 has been put forth as the next evolutionary phase of industrial and technological advancement, building upon the cyber-physical systems integration promised by Industry 4.0. While Industry 4.0 focused predominantly on automating and digitizing manufacturing through advanced computerization, Industry 5.0, also known as Society 5.0, aims to leverage these technological capabilities to solve pressing social problems (Gürdür Broo et al., 2022). The capabilities developed in the name of optimized production are now intended to directly tackle challenges like inequality, climate change, education gaps, and healthcare access. Industry 5.0 seeks convergence between economic goals and social values which involves using the same technologies and approaches to further problems. However, as we have explored, the unchecked proliferation of anthropocentric intelligent machines risks exacerbating ecological destruction and human alienation from nature. Therefore, a truly harmonious Society 5.0 must move beyond human-centered design approaches toward an ecocentric orientation that promotes technology in service of all life.

Replacing anthropocentric priorities with ecocentric ones signals a philosophical shift that aligns with the underlying goals of Industry 5.0. Creating intelligent machines that enrich our shared environment and stabilize threatened ecosystems would significantly contribute to solving major societal challenges like climate change, pollution, and biodiversity loss. This does not mean, however, that human interests will be deliberately harmed or ignored. On the contrary, pursuing ecocentric technology design would also foster a renewed sense of human belonging within nature, addressing issues of purpose and loneliness. Intelligent machines that promote ecological health could help restore balance to disrupted biotic networks, allowing both human and more-than-human communities to thrive in synergy.

While anthropocentric machines have undoubtedly revolutionized various aspects of human life, they also animate valid concerns regarding their impact on society and the environment. By encouraging human-centric perspectives, fostering unsustainable consumption patterns, and shaping our self-images and interactions with others, these machines may intensify detrimental relationships with our environments. As we continue to develop and integrate intelligent technologies, it becomes imperative to strike a balance that fosters a more ecocentric approach—one that considers the well-being of both humanity and the planet, recognizing the intrinsic value of all living beings and the interconnectedness of our world.

In essence, whereas the anthropocentric design of intelligent machines myopically focuses solely on human interests (to the minimization and erosion of others'), adopting a wider ecocentric perspective may serve to benefit both humans and nature. To sustain the existence of a range of lifeforms and allow nature to flourish, we must cultivate fundamentally ecocentric machine designs that enrich, rather than vitiate, our planet's ecosystems. This requires a profound mindset shift—prioritizing ecological wholeness instead of human supremacy. It means designing intelligent systems that serve to stabilize, rather than disrupt, the biotic networks from which we have arisen and upon which we depend. Recognizing the profound pitfalls of extreme anthropocentrism, we must start to envision technologies harmoniously embedded within, rather than extracted from and destructive toward, the existing natural ecosystems.

Two obvious concerns related to ecocentric machines are a) that they might be perceived as anti-humanistic b) and that it is difficult to imagine who would have the incentive to develop, produce and deploy such machines. Deep ecology, for example, has been criticized as being *anti-human* or misanthropic, as one might interpret the philosophy as inimical both to human interests and humans in general (Drengson, 1995). For example, Næss (1989) repeatedly points to humans as the source of the ecological challenge we face and indicates that we could both be fewer and that we should limit our activities drastically. This, some argue, would be deeply inimical to, for example, utilitarian notions related to promoting *ethical* decisions by aiming for the greatest good for the greatest number of people (i.e., *humans*). Reducing human numbers and human material welfare as we measure it today could then be seen as inimical to human interests. Furthermore, modern notions of sustainable development (Brundtland, 1987) and the Sustainable Development Goals (United Nations, 2015) are premised on the idea that growth is required to meet human interests, and that environmental challenges are problematic insofar as they threaten *human* interests (Sætra, 2023). A *fully* ecocentric machine might in theory end up combatting humans in order to promote better balance between species and to allow for the flourishing of non-humans. In the extreme, it might even determine that humans are, at the very core, a cancerous growth that must be eliminated to promote life and flourishing more generally, as imagined in various science fiction scenarios in which alignment problems between humans and machines are considered. The second concern relates to incentives, as one might argue that it is very unlikely that any corporation, for example, would develop and deploy a machine that is not aimed at promoting its interests. If they do make machines to monitor biological diversity in an area, for example

because they depend on the ecosystem services produced by the natural environment, this would still be highly anthropocentric, and not a fully ecocentric machine. These concerns are real and important, and they also point towards the conclusion that *fully* ecocentric machines might be neither desirable nor probable. Even the most ardent environmentalist will most likely support introducing some sort of guard-rails ensuring that the machines will not challenge human survival, for example. This still allows for machines that are much further towards the ecocentric side of the continuum than the machines we explored in the historical review, and this could still have highly beneficial consequences for environmental sustainability.

In the following section, we offer suggestions as to how intelligent machines can transition from a deeply problematic anthropocentric approach to design to a more ethically defensible standard of ecocentrism.

6. Strategies to move from Anthropocentrism toward Ecocentrism

Shifting design of future intelligent machines from an anthropocentric to an ecocentric orientation requires fundamental changes in the mindsets and priorities of engineers. This section outlines four key strategies to catalyze this transition.

6.1. Strategy 1: Moving from problem-solving towards question-seeking

The formal training of engineers, in the modern sense, is only 150+ years old (Shaw, 2002) yet we are required to reimagine the field in response to rapid technological changes (G. Downey, 2005). Comparative historical research on engineering (G. L. Downey & Lucena, 2004) reveals that even though the definition of engineering and engineering knowledge varied greatly over time and from place to place, a distinctive commonality existed – the commitment to technological change and focus on technical problem-solving (G. Downey, 2005). Therefore, the problem-solving skills of engineers are invaluable and unreplaceable. Yet, in today’s technology-driven engineering practices, problem definition and creativity are becoming as important as problem-solving abilities (G. Downey, 2005; Gürdür Broo et al., 2022). While the future cannot be designed explicitly, the artifacts that we create today will partially constitute the future that is tomorrow (Parrish, 2007). Design is a way of organizing those artifacts, both human activity systems, and technologies, so that they may contribute to an envisioned future. Herbert Simon distinguished the natural sciences which are concerned with explaining how things are from design sciences which are concerned with how things ought to be (Kessler, 2013) that is, with devising artifacts to attain goals. Different than engineering, the design discipline provides us a way to think unboundedly without being limited by problems. While designing incorporates analytical, synthetic, divergent, and convergent thinking to create a wide number of potential solutions, it is more than problem-solving. It is also question-finding.

Today’s practices concerning the design of intelligent machines are focused on problem-solving, and they are not able to support the level that is desired in reaching Industry 5.0 or Sustainable Development Goals, where design for benefitting society is the key. Therefore, we should start to focus on question-seeking, along with providing answers/solutions for these questions. Efforts like design thinking (Brown, 2009) and more-than-human design (Foth et al. 2021; Coşkun et al. 2022) offer useful approaches along these lines. Ultimately, the question-seeking task is a great way to reach more ecocentric intelligent machines. The ability to ask questions –and even to ask difficult questions that may not have any set answers– is one of the most important skills to extend our long-term view beyond the current practices when designing sustainable and resilient future ecosystems.

To put this strategy into practice, engineers should devote time in the design process to open-ended inquiry before rushing to solve assumed problems. Building organizational capacity for discovery-driven basic research unrelated to commercial outcomes can liberate creativity. Education programs should train students in divergent thinking, philosophically-grounded questioning, and contemplative methods to counterbalance technical problem-solving.

6.2. Strategy 2: Moving from networks towards ecosystems

In engineering and computer science networks are very well-studied. The first computer network goes back to 1956 (Earnest, 2014). These connected computers later evolved into the Internet. Today, we are still working on connecting more computers, sensors, Internet of Things, vehicles, infrastructure, etc. to build new or enlarge existing networks. These entities use common communication protocols over digital interconnections to communicate with each other. Networks are based on protocols and exchange information/resources.

Ecosystems are driven by mutual purpose and include development actions (Handbook, 2021). Britannica defines an ecosystem as “the complex of living organisms, their physical environment, and all their interrelationships in a particular unit of space” (Britannica, 2023). Ecology science is the scientific study of how life forms interact and coexist. Ecosystems are dynamic and, more importantly, ecosystems function as one unified unit whereas networks do not need to have a common purpose and focus on integrations (Handbook, 2021). Ecological systems or ecosystems consist of all the organisms and the physical environment with which they

interact. Current implementations of digital ecosystems (Boley & Chang, 2007; Chang & West, 2006; Li et al., 2012) are limited to software and, regrettably, the definition of digital ecosystems is not reflecting the many opportunities that biological ecosystems present. Frequently the word 'ecosystem' is merely used for branding purposes without any inherent ecological properties (Briscoe, 2009; Granstrand & Holgersson, 2020).

Many from engineering and technology domains agree that we should move towards more dynamic new ecosystems instead of only integrating existing systems through networks. For instance, just this year, the vice president of Gartner, David Groombridge (Gartner, 2022) said that "self-managing physical or software systems that learn from their environments in the longer term, will become common in physical systems such as robots, drones, manufacturing machines, and smart spaces." To be able to build these systems in the future, we should already from today start to think about how to enable our systems to be resilient, sustainable, and collaborative.

We should go beyond designing networks of intelligent machines and use natural ecosystems as inspiration for designing next-generation machines as constituent parts of larger ecosystems driven by prerogatives like maintenance, integrity, and preservation of diversity. This ecosystemic view could enable future intelligent systems to pursue their own goals while contributing to a common purpose.

This strategy requires modeling intelligent machines less as isolated nodes and more as interdependent participants in complex systems. Adopting lifecycle thinking to evaluate total impacts can reveal harmful system-level effects. Designing machines to support the health of surrounding ecosystems requires assessing functionality beyond narrow technical metrics. We should expand design constraints and success criteria to include social and environmental considerations. Taking inspiration from nature's systemic wisdom can nurture values like holism, diversity, and sustainability.

6.3. Strategy 3: Moving from exploitation towards exploration

Another important strategy involves the interplay between exploration and exploitation. In different research domains from behavioral science to computer science, the exploration-exploitation trade-off is studied and used to explain different strategies. It can be related to exploitation versus exploration (in decision-making research) (Cohen et al., 2007; March, 1991); focused versus diffuse (in cognitive research) (Treisman & Gelade, 1980; Wolfe et al., 1989), intensive versus extensive (in foraging research) (Benhamou, 2007), local versus global (in memory) (T. Hills et al., 2009), and depth-first versus breadth-first (in artificial intelligence) (Korf, 1985).

While exploitation focuses on exploiting known opportunities, exploration searches for new possibilities. Seeking a goal under uncertainty is a ubiquitous requirement of life. Animals forage for food, territory, and mates; humans engage in a wide variety of search behaviors, from looking for lost items to finding opportunities or to seeking the meaning of existence. Search, experimentation, taking a risk, discovery, and innovation involve trade-offs between exploiting and exploring (T. T. Hills et al., 2015). March's (1991) well-known theoretical framework of exploration and exploitation focuses on understanding how organizations remain innovative and what role organizational learning plays in this process. The research findings show that to maintain competitiveness, organizations exploit their existing capabilities and expertise but also explore novel ways of doing things. While the exploitation strategies may help with rapid development and are likely to become effective in the short run, self-destruction is inevitable in the long run (March, 1991).

The reasoning behind focusing on exploration in the proposed project is not due to unsuccessful exploitation results in engineering; it is rather due to not enough exploration activities found in current practices. The current engineering environments in industry and academia are heavily restricted by many constraints, including those related to resources, finances, and culture, among others. Research from industrial organizations, technology and operations management, organizational behavior, and similar fields has focused on understanding the effects of these various constraints. The fragmented and conflicting findings show that constraints can both hinder and foster creativity and innovation (Acar et al., 2019). To develop ecocentric design solutions, we need more exploration, and we need scientists, engineers, and innovators who relentlessly explore different domains, and dare to go after impossible ideas even when we know that there is a risk of failure. While exploitation is safe, exploration requires us to embrace uncertainty.

To reorient technology design from exploitation toward exploration, institutions can incentivize serendipitous knowledge gains over optimizations confined by convention. Diversifying design requirements beyond efficiency and productivity metrics creates space for experimentation. Education predicated on standardization and certainty should incorporate more play, ambiguity, and discovery-based learning. Mentorships, informal collaborations, and interdisciplinary networks can spark unexpected innovation when exploitation seems exhausted. Exploration is risky, but breaking routine yields ground-breaking insights.

6.4. Strategy 4: Moving from monodisciplinarity towards transdisciplinarity

One way to explore new possibilities is to observe the world around us and transfer knowledge from different disciplines—such as ecological science to engineering. The concept of transdisciplinarity is defined as “a common system of axioms for a set of disciplines” (Fernandes & Philippi Jr., 2017) transcending the narrow scope of disciplinary worldviews through an overarching synthesis (Klein, 2020). It deals with research problems that emanate from complex and heterogeneous domains (Lawrence, 2004; Lawrence & Després, 2004; Ng & To, 2020). Max-Neef (2005) argues that “transdisciplinarity, more than a new discipline or super-discipline is, actually, a different manner of seeing the world, more systemic and more holistic.” While interdisciplinarity serves to enable the construction of common models or transfer of tools between disciplines, transdisciplinarity goes one step further in the science/society interface (Muhar et al., 2013; Tejedor et al., 2018) and instead focuses on articulations, preserving the different realities and confronting them in a controlled way.

The 21st century is characterized by rapid change, uncertainty, and increasing interconnectedness (Morin & Kern, 1999). Rapid change is due to the continuous technological advancements from higher processing power to increased data capabilities. Uncertainty is due to this continuous rapid change and unprecedented events, such as Covid-19. Interconnectedness refers not only to technological advancements such as the Internet for connecting people and computers, but also the interactions between machines. Moreover, the grand challenges of this century, including climate change (and associated extreme weather events), water scarcity, air pollution, forced migrations, poverty, deforestation, rising inequalities, pandemics, and more, are complex problems (Gürdür Broo, 2021). They encompass interdependent systems and pluralism of values within societies and thus require a holistic view. They simply cannot be adequately tackled from the sphere of specific individual disciplines (Max-Neef, 2005) but require the consideration of different perspectives using multiple lenses.

Benyus (1997) summarizes the reasoning behind looking at nature as an example by stating that “after 3.8 billion years of research and development, failures are fossils, and what surrounds us is the secret to survival.” Ecology-inspired design will be the practice of mimicking natural ecosystems in order to imagine and design new engineered ecosystems. It assumes that nature is creative by necessity and that over eons of time, it has evolved countless sustainable solutions as ecosystems (Marshall, 2007). Researchers from different disciplines are already working on adjacent ideas. For instance, Connop & Nash, (2021) see nature-inspired design as an antidote to urban built environments from an architectural perspective. Yuchi et al. (2007) studied an ecology-inspired strategy for parent selection and applied it to numerical constrained optimization problems from a mathematics perspective. Intelligent machine design and development efforts should operationalize similar approaches to find the best cases and inspirations for ecocentric approaches.

Putting this strategy into practice, involves transcending narrow disciplinary boundaries through cross-pollination of diverse perspectives. Engineers should proactively seek solutions from other fields like ecology to expand their knowledge base. Learning exchanges with environmental experts and participatory design practices can bridge divides. Holistic systems modeling requires synthesizing technical and philosophical modes of inquiry. Cultivating intellectual humility opens new possibilities and challenges entrenched assumptions. Ultimately, transdisciplinarity integrates varied ways of understanding our complex world.

7. Conclusion

This study aimed to understand how intelligent machines are designed and used throughout history. We show how anthropocentrism has been the driving force behind the design and application of these systems. To be able to design the next generation of intelligent machines in a more ecocentric manner, we proposed four strategies: moving from (1) problem-solving to question-seeking; (2) networks to ecosystems; (3) exploitation to exploration; and (4) monodisciplinarity to transdisciplinarity.

Divining inspiration from nature is neither a new or untested idea. The idea of investigating nature for inspiration often reaches back to Aristotle and his idea of flourishing. He famously said that “one thing alone cannot meaningfully flourish.” His student Theophrastus was probably the first one who tried to understand the ecological relationships between the plants and the landscape. From Charles Darwin to Eugene Warmin to Heinrich Muller, many contributed to the theories in ecological sciences and natural history. One of Einstein’s most famous quotes is “look deep, deep into nature, and then you will understand everything better.” For centuries successive industrial revolutions have idealized man-made systems and consciously or unconsciously adopted an anthropocentric approach to the design of technology. In this study, we propose an alternative—to pursue an ecocentric perspective when thinking about future intelligent machines—in order to change how our future will be designed. De-centering humanity from its long-occupied place atop the moral hierarchy is, we argue, necessary to ensure that humans and nonhumans alike are around to see the fruits of their creative labors now and into the distant future.

This study has significant impact across multiple dimensions. Conceptually, it expands the discourse on

technology ethics by proposing ecocentrism as an alternative paradigm for intelligent machine design. This philosophical contribution provides a new values-based framework for assessing and guiding technical systems. Methodologically, the blended historical and systems thinking approach demonstrates an integrative way to analyze engineering habits and identify leverage points for change. This model enables disciplined critique of persistent blind spots, yielding potential transformations. Practically, the proposed strategies offer tangible guidance to researchers, developers, and policymakers seeking to implement more ecologically-aligned intelligent machines. By questioning deeply rooted anthropocentric assumptions and outlining pathways to an ecocentric orientation, this research has wide-ranging influence on how intelligent machines are envisioned, studied, created, and governed. Fundamentally, it aims to broaden considerations in technology design to better account for the interests of the more-than-human world, driving progress toward more just, responsible, and environmentally sustainable technical systems. The conceptual, methodological, and applied contributions of this study can instigate meaningful conversations and positive changes.

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